

PERCEPTION OF STUDENTS AND TEACHERS TOWARDS ONLINE CLASS: A STUDY IN BALASORE AND BHADRAK DISTRICT OF ODISHA

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Abstract

The study explores the perceptions of higher secondary school students and teachers in Bhadrak and Balasore districts of Odisha, towards online class. The study was conducted on a sample of 150 teachers and 151 students. The research identifies factors influencing their perceptions, such as technical issues, comfort level, support, and training. Results reveal significant differences between students and teachers perceptions, indicating areas for improvement in online learning experiences. Recommendations include enhancing teaching practices, training, and support to address these disparities and improve overall effectiveness. Despite limitations, the study provides valuable insights for policy makers, educational institutions, and course facilitators in designing and implementing online learning initiatives, particularly in the context of the evolving landscape of education.

Keywords: Online classes; Students Perception; Teachers Perception

Introduction

While e-learning has witnessed significant growth and adoption in India, it remains a work in progress. The ongoing evolution of technology, coupled with concerted efforts to address existing challenges, holds the potential to unlock the full promise of online education, making learning more accessible, flexible, and effective for learners across the country. In this scenario, the role played by teachers and students gains due importance as it is their perceptions and attitude, which is critical to motivation and learning (Koohang and Durante, 2003). Ultimately it is the acceptance of students and teachers that helps in reaping the benefits of online classes (Botas,2008)

Review of Related Literature: Lin (2015) conducted a survey on teaching practices and teacher perceptions in online World Language Courses, Using survey and interview data. This study examines online language teachers' teaching practices, their adjustments toward online teaching, and the professional development (PD) that they received and expected to receive in a virtual high school in the United States. Cheok et al. (2017) focused on teachers' perceptions of E-Learning in Malaysian Secondary Schools. Samples (Participants) in this study were 60 teachers from three secondary schools from two states in Malaysia. They were randomly selected after their schools were identified as being among the top users of the FROG VLE. Todd (2020) focused on teachers' perceptions of the shift from the classroom to online teaching. To understand the impact of the shift, a survey of all 52 English language teachers at one respected Thailand University was conducted with two main focuses. Kulal and Anupam (2020) studied the perception of teachers and students towards online classes in Dakshina Kannada and Udupi District. Meşe and Sevilen (2021) conducted a qualitative case study was in order to explore students' perceptions of online teaching and how it affects their motivation over a period of a seven-week-course. Both interviews and creative writing tasks demonstrated that students overall believe online education had a negative impact on their motivation due to lack of social interaction, a mismatch between expectations implications are listed.

This research aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the perceptions of higher secondary school students and teachers towards online classes, paving the way for a more effective and equitable learning environment. Further, this study will contribute to a better understanding of how online classes can be effectively implemented in higher secondary education, ultimately improving the learning experience for all stakeholders

Objectives of the Study: This study was guided by the following objectives

1. To study the factors that determine the perception of higher secondary school students towards online classes.
2. To study the factors that determines the perception of higher secondary school teachers towards online classes.
3. To compare the perception of higher secondary school teachers and students towards online classes.

Hypotheses of the Study: Considering the above objectives, the study has the following hypotheses.

1. H₀₁: There is no significant difference of perception of teachers' and students towards online class in higher secondary school.

2. H₀₂: There is no significant difference of perception of male teachers' and female teachers towards online classes in higher secondary school.

3. H₀₃: There is no significant difference of perception of Arts teachers' and Science teachers towards online classes in higher secondary school.

Methodology: For the present study sample was selected using purposive sampling technique. Further, due to time and cost restrictions, 10 schools in Bhadrak district and 10 schools in Balasore district of Odisha were chosen. The information regarding the online learning and teaching perception followed in these organizations was gathered through Google questionnaire. Online questionnaires were also sent to the respondents on their WhatsApp numbers as well as via email. A sample of 150 teachers was taken from both Bhadrak and Balasore district government higher secondary schools. A sample of 151 students each were selected from both Bhadrak and Balasore district government higher secondary schools. The entire process of data collection was carried out online from January, 2022 to April, 2022.

Major Findings of the Study

- a) There was a significant difference between perception of teachers and students towards online class.
- b) The study did not find the gender as a factor that differentiates the perception between male teacher and female teacher towards online class.
- c) The study finds the subject (curriculum) as a factor that makes the significant difference between perception of teachers' and students towards online class.
- d) The study finds the factors such as impact, support and Comfortability that determine the perception of students towards online class.
- e) The study finds the factors such as teaching practices, training, development, and efficacy that determine the perception of teachers towards online class.

The researchers in the present study came to the conclusion that there was significant difference between teachers' perception towards online classes and student's perception towards such as comfortability, understanding, conversant with technology etc. do affect the online classes. There is no significantly difference between perception of male teachers' and female teachers towards online class. The result can be further concluded that the factor gender does not affect perception of male teachers and female teachers towards online class. After doing the EFA, the study finds the three factors i.e., impact, comfortability and support of students' perception towards online learning and teaching. Further, EFA was undertaken on collected information of perception of teachers towards on online learning and teaching. The

study finds three factors such as teaching practice, training and development and efficacy of teachers' perception towards online learning and teaching. Students must have high-speed internet access at home. Asynchronous online education gives students control over their learning experiences allows flexibility in the curriculum for non-traditional students, and gives students greater responsibility.

Educational Implications of the Study

- a) Online class for students improves student accessibility. Students must be organized, self-motivated, and have a high level of time management to participate in an online programme.
- b) Online learning methods can be an effective alternative educational medium for mature and self-disciplined pupils but are unsuitable for learning environments that depend on the learner.
- c) It is essential for teachers to keep their online lessons clear, engaging, and interactive so that students can concentrate on the lessons. Students' commitment to time is often misinterpreted as meaning that online courses require less time and effort than traditional courses.
- d) Online students can participate in internal class discussions and complete assignments, essays, and projects.
- e) Online learning can lead to students not developing the necessary communicative skills. In addition, students must have high-speed internet access at home, which can lead to complications if it is not available.
- f) Asynchronous online education gives students control over their learning experience, allows flexibility in the curriculum for non-traditional students, and gives students greater responsibility.
- g) Through the use of online learning, students can distance themselves from each other without being exposed to coronavirus and online learning has many health benefits for students and their families.

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